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AN ILLUMINATION OF 3rd YEAR, THAI ENGLISH-MAJOR UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS OF NATIVE AND THAI ENGLISH TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative research study examines 158 Thai EFL, 3rd-year, undergraduate students' perceptions of Thai English teachers (TETs) and Native English teachers (NETs). The purposive convenience sample was three English-major cohorts studying at UBRU, Thailand. A content analysis of 158 'Compare and Contrast' essays entitled 'Thai English Teachers and Native English teachers' was conducted and followed repetitive reading and coding of the data. The initial twenty-four identified codes were collapsed into five code groups. These groups were then collapsed further into two emerging themes. The research indicates that the students prefer NETs when learning Listening, Speaking and Writing skills and preferred TETs when learning Grammar. The students also clearly indicated a preference for the varied, interactive activity based teaching methods employed by NETs over the didactic, textbook, grammar-translation methods used by the TETs. The limited use of L1 in the EFL classroom was perceived as appropriate because it enabled understanding of complicated grammar concepts. It also reduced students' interactive anxiety. The students did however indicate a preference for NETs when their perceived proficiency levels are higher. This study should aid readers understanding of Thai EFL undergraduate students and inform teaching staff about important considerations when developing EFL educational programmes in Thailand.

Keywords:

Student Perception, Thai & Native English Teachers, Content Analysis, Qualitative Thematic Research.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the latter part of the 20th century and into the 21st century, English has developed into the most internationally spoken language (Foley, 2006). An ever increasing number of people are now learning English as a second or foreign language (ESL, EFL) (Block, 2002; Crystal, 2003; Holliday, 2005; Nunan, 2001). World Languages and Cultures (2010) identify the important benefits of learning English in the global market as: (a) improving global understanding, (b) increasing potential employment, (c) improving chances for accessing higher education institutions, (d) increasing options for studying abroad, and (e) improving the understanding of alternative cultures.

The growing demand for English language education and the growing need for well-qualified English Language teachers have become increasingly important in Thailand. This has contributed to the international debate about who is best equipped to teach English as a foreign language (EFL); native or non-native English teachers? There is an assumption that Native English Teachers (NETs) are better than Non-Native English Teachers (NNETs) (Davies, 2003), however what constitutes as ‘better’ is not so clearly defined and appears to vary.

The use of the terms native and non-native English speaker is contentious (Cook, 1999; Liu, 2007; Medgyes, 1992). For teachers of English, this dichotomy is very personal and raises issues of professional credibility, power, and status, (Braine, 1999; Cook, 1999; Lui, 1999b). However, researchers continue to use the terms ‘native’ and ‘non-native’, because of the lack of a more suitable distinction and the apparent acceptance of these terms. Much of the current research in this area has focused on English language teachers’ self-perceptions as native or non-native speakers, teachers’ perceptions of their colleagues and their respective ‘advantages’ (McNeill, 1994), and teachers’ perceptions of their students’ perceptions of them, in the EFL classroom (Lui, 1999b; McNeill, 1994; Reves & Medgyes, 1994).

There is, however, one issue that is largely missing from the literature and that is the EFL learners’ perceptions of native and non-native English teachers in the EFL classroom, especially within Thailand. Of the few studies reviewing student perceptions of native or non-native English speaking teachers, none of the students were Thai (Filho, 2002; Mahboob, 2003; Lasagabaster & Sierra, 2002; Rubin, 1995). Thus, a primary goal of this study is to identify and categorise the perceptions of academic Thai EFL learners, in an attempt to develop a deeper understanding of this phenomena. As a result, the learners being reviewed will shine a light on the missing but important viewpoint in the overall conversation about native and non-native English teachers in Thailand.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In the EFL classroom, learners’ exposure to English is restricted. Gass and Selinker (2001) identify 3 sources of exposure to English, “(1) teacher, (2) materials, and (3) other learners”. The NET is often the only exposure the EFL learners have to proficient English, and in Thailand, learners’ exposure to English is often limited to only NNETs. These interactions are often filled with errors (Lightbown & Spada, 1999).

When reviewing the issues of English education in Thailand it is important to review Thailand's status. When compared to international English proficiency, Thailand is somewhat lacking. A report published by EF EPI (2011) highlighted the relative ranking of the English proficiency of young adults. At that time, Thailand was ranked 42nd out of 44 countries, which is in the 'very low proficiency' category. This is despite all schoolchildren in Thailand being taught English throughout their education. Both Indonesia and Vietnam were in the same, 'very low proficiency' category in the 2011 report, being ranked 34th and 39th respectively. Throughout the time that the EF EPI has been reporting, Thailand has remained in the 'very low proficiency' group, despite both Vietnam and Indonesia having moved up two levels to the 'moderate proficiency' category, being ranked 29th and 32nd out of 70 countries, respectively (EPI Report 2015). Thailand is currently ranked 62nd out of 70 countries. Thailand's English proficiency remains poor when compared to the ASEAN community and Asia in general. "Thailand's English proficiency remains [worryingly] low and is trending down the rankings, despite the country's large tourism industry" (EPI Report 2015 p.26).

Most Thai universities are unable to meet the demands for English used in the workplace. This is because the listening and speaking skills needed in the workplace are not the skills focussed on in the Thai tertiary education English curricula (Wiriyaichitra 2013). Wiriyaichitra (2013) goes on to indicate that class sizes (45-60), and the insufficient English language skills of TETs, contribute to Thailand's very low English proficiency. The students are motivated to learn English but suffer difficulties caused by a lack of opportunity to practice and use English, unchallenging English lessons, being passive learners, being too shy to use English with classmates, and a lack of responsibility for their own learning. The National Education Act adopted in 1997 seeks to reform all education in Thailand. However, it must be noted that teachers tend to teach the way they were taught and that the process of change is likely to be much slower than anticipated.

Both Noon-Ura (2013) and Wiriyaichitra (2013), highlight the contemporary failings of the current English education practice in Thailand and clearly identify a need for change. Understanding students' perspectives is an important stage in moving in a new direction. The vast majority of research conducted in this area is based on statistically analysing questionnaire data, which fails to clearly identify what the students express in their own words.

SUBJECTIVE OBSERVATIONS PRECEDING THE STUDY

The research paradigm used in this study is deeply rooted in qualitative phenomenological concepts. As such, it is of great importance to describe the background of the study in relation to the researcher's experiences teaching English in Thailand since 2010.

In 2010, the researcher soon became comfortable working with new colleagues. Although most were courteous and warm, there were some that seemed reluctant to engage in any conversation. The researcher was later informed that this reluctance was due to their own feelings of inadequacy using English with an Englishman, even though they were professionally employed as university English teachers. It seemed rather odd to the researcher as to why the TETs did not want to practice and maintain their English language skills.

What was very different too was the students' passivity in the classroom and their reluctance to use English, which appeared to emulate the teachers' reluctance. However, after developing positive working relationships with the students they quickly appeared comfortable, attentive, and communicated in English, albeit reluctantly at times within the EFL classroom. They continued to use only Thai outside of the classroom and for much of the time in the classroom with TETs.

The students were often heard complaining about the Thai teachers. They complained of boredom in their TET classrooms and felt they were not learning. The students would show the researcher work they were expected to complete that far exceeded their current ability and they were constantly bombarded with non-context-based grammar exercises. They expressed boredom and bewilderment, often asking the researcher to help them understand their TET homework, as it was beyond their proficiency levels. Interestingly, the TETs would often ask the researcher to check their student materials prior to their classes as they were unable to understand the work themselves. The researcher always obliged along with the simple question of why the teacher was asking the students to perform at a proficiency level that was beyond their own ability.

The researcher found it difficult to identify any consistent predetermined parity of English level between the student modules. An example is the students being expected to translate level 4-6 text with understanding in one module, where they are unable to read or write at level 2 in other modules taken simultaneously. They were also taught to constantly translate all English into Thai in order to understand. The researcher frequently witnessed English being taught only using Thai and often saw students presenting information to their Thai English teachers and their fellow students, in Thai. The Thai teachers were often sitting in the corner of the room behind a desk as a barrier, teaching from textbooks.

Some teaching staff squarely blame the inadequacies of Thai EFL learning on the students, stating that they are all lazy. In fact, during the researcher's initial interview, the researcher was told not to expect much from the students as they were primarily from farming backgrounds. So are many Vietnamese and Indonesian students and as previously identified, their English proficiency levels have improved dramatically over the past 4 years. There was also a denial from some senior TETs of the failings of undergraduate English education in Thailand, despite this being frequently identified and discussed in academia, the international public media, and by the ASEAN community. The final motivation for undertaking this study was the reading of a promotional article that suggested that native English teachers were unnecessary in Thailand and that the advertiser's English school offered Thai only teachers. Ironically, the article contained numerous grammar errors.

Thailand is culturally proud, patriarchal, and religious, with a rigid hierarchical structure. The loss of face that is to be persistently avoided, at times leads to a rejection of or non-acknowledgement of evidence or opinion from subordinates that goes against Thai contemporary accepted norms, and usually means that critical analysis is often not accepted. This also means that the acceptance of a need to change and change itself is rather difficult. Especially if the issues raised or solutions offered are made by a foreigner.

The EFL educational problems are complicated and diverse and appear to be rooted in Thai educational and cultural norms. However, the subjective nature of the identification of these problems needs to be expanded upon and understood in a systematic way. The researcher therefore, decided to investigate and attempt to understand in more detail the students' perceptions of native and Thai English teachers.

In order to truly help people they must first accept that they would benefit from the help.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this research is to formally identify and categorise the sample EFL students' differing perceptions of Native English teachers (NETs) and Thai English-teachers (TETs), using their own words. That is, the purpose of the study is to gain a full and comprehensive understanding of the true cultural nature of how the Thai students perceive Thai and native English teachers.

This study does not focus on identifying and determining which teacher group is better at teaching English. Nor does it seek to promote one group of teachers over another. It focusses entirely on the students' perceptions regarding their NETs and TETs, as written in their own words, as part of a compare and contrast essay. It aims to create greater awareness and recognition of the strengths, weaknesses, and differences of NETs and TETs, as perceived by their students, so both teacher groups and their students can benefit. This should ultimately lead to an improvement in educational practice that is more closely aligned to student requirements. It is not a critique of current practice per say, although it does seek to open windows of future educational improvements in Thailand. This study's findings should enable NETs and TETs' to develop a better understanding of their distinct characteristics of teaching and so enable them to build effective curricula and utilise effective pragmatic teaching methodologies, by learning from each other's uniqueness. Additionally, by discussing the challenging and positive EFL students' classroom experiences, the teachers should be able to adapt to the needs of the students rather than focus on the needs of the teachers. Hopefully, NETs and TETs could have opportunities to realise how to improve their English teaching to better serve the needs of EFL students. Lastly, this study could be used as a platform for further study in the field of EFL education in Thailand as a developing phenomenon.

It is only with a comprehensive understanding of the students' perceptions that an honest appraisal of the needs of the students can be achieved. Teachers are there to serve the needs of the students, maintain academic standards, and advance educational practice by engaging in meaningful research and implementing beneficial research findings that focus upon pragmatic education. It is the teachers who are responsible for setting up and maintaining healthy and productive educational environment where the students can; feel motivated, progressively learn, feel safe, and achieve.

Prior research with empirical studies have stressed the perception of advantages and disadvantages between NETs and NNETs and then attributed the differences to the teachers' classroom behaviours (Arva & Medgyes, 2000; Benke & Medgyes, 2005; Kirkpatrick, 2006; Lasagabaster & Sierra, 2002; Medgyes, 1992, 1993), which neglected students' perceptions.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- 1) What phrases and sentences do Thai English major undergraduate students use to describe their perceptions of Native English teachers and Thai English teachers?
- 2) What codes and coding groups can be identified from the students' perceptions of native English teachers and Thai English Teachers?
- 3) What emergent themes that can be identified following analysis of text that can be used to aid the understanding of the data?

SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This research highlights the variety and extent of Thai EFL students' perceptions within the English department at UBRU. The large volume of data is rich with a plethora of identified accurate perceptions, which are needed for the purpose of this research. However, it is important to identify the limitations of the research. The subjective nature of qualitative research means that the data is not generalizable to a wider population. The 'snapshot' data capture is also limited, as it does not allow for any changes over time, or understanding of how the students' perceptions may change as they progress through their undergraduate learning. There could also be a tendency to make the researcher the cited example of the native English teacher as all the participating students' most recent experience of a native teacher was with the researcher. This may cause the data to be about the researcher and TETs rather than be about NETs and TETs. Group dynamics also states that the cohort groups will likely share their educational satisfactions and dissatisfactions amongst themselves. This means that the identification of individually generated perceptions will be very difficult to portray. In a sense, the data will more likely be the result of collective, previously shared and agreed upon, perceptions. This will not dilute the quality of the data but it would make comparison very difficult between, for example, genders, English proficiency levels, or age. Finally, the structured essay instrument could limit the students recording of all their thoughts and perceptions, as they were limited to record only their three most important perceptions of similarity and three of difference. The honesty of participants would definitely influence the reliability of the findings in this research study.

RELATED LITERATURE

The term "nativeness" is frequently discussed in EFL research and means "who is a native speaker of English and who is not" (Al-Omrani, 2008). However Braine (1999) and Mahboob (2004), suggest there is no precise definition for "native speaker," as it is not possible to empirically define what a native speaker is. Lightbown and Spada (1999) define a native speaker as a person who has learned a language from an early age and who has full mastery of the language. Cook (1999) explains that ultimately, the "indisputable element in the definition of a native speaker is that a person is a native speaker of the language learnt first..." It would seem then that the place of birth is less important than language competence and the early exposure to English. This is clearly evident where young children who immigrated to the UK from non-English speaking countries learned English language as their first language. Despite their abilities and competence, they are not accepted in Thailand as 'native' English speakers.

NETs have definite advantages in the classroom. Reves and Medgyes (1994) report that NETs; were more motivational and able to create an 'English' environment, taught how to use English rather than about the English language, and used effective and innovative teaching methods. NETs are also better at teaching in specific skill areas such as pronunciation or culture. Filho (2002), suggests that most students prefer a native speaker for culture, communication skills, and pronunciation classes. Ulate (2011) indicated that NETs exhibited the following characteristics: (1) subconscious knowledge of rules, (2) intuitive grasp of meanings, (3) ability to communicate within social settings, (4) range of language skills, (5) creativity of language use, (6) identification with a language community, (7) ability to produce fluent discourse, (8) knowledge of differences between their own speech and that of the "standard" form of the language, and (9) ability to interpret and translate into the L1. Widdowson (1992) stated that a NET would be a reliable informant of linguistic knowledge due to their personal native language learning experiences. Stern (1983) noted that NETs' linguistic knowledge, proficiency, and competence of the target language were crucial for language proficiency in English teaching.

Conversely, Medgyes (1993) noted that NNETs have advantages in terms of six characteristics: (1) good role models for imitation, (2) effective providers of learning strategies, (3) suppliers of information about the English language, (4) better anticipators of language learning difficulties, (5) sensitive and empathetic to language learners' needs and problems, and (6) facilitators of language learning as a result of a shared mother tongue. Whilst these points are both important and valid, they are based on an assumption that the NET has not had experience learning a second language. NNETs' personal experience of how the mother tongue and the target language differed and what was difficult for learners provides direct insight into the linguistic and cultural needs of learners.

NETs' weaknesses include: different linguistic and cultural backgrounds from learners, a difficulty of perceive the difficulties of learning the target language, and a lack of familiarity with learners' learning contexts (Barratt and Kontra, 2000). They also indicated that learners were easily discouraged because NETs rarely made useful comparison and contrasts with the learner's first language, nor did they empathize with students going through the learning process. Boyle (1997) indicated that NETs may understand the accuracy in grammar but were not able to explain language rules like NNETs could. However, there is no clear link between having descriptive knowledge of a language and having a pragmatic ability to use a language. By definition, NETs have a very clear and obvious pragmatic ability to use English, despite their lowered ability to describe the nuances of the grammatical structures of English. One must therefore question the need to focus on grammar at the expense of pragmatic utility of English.

It is undeniable that NNETs are not as competent as NETs in speaking aspects. NNETs' weaknesses were also highlighted by Moussu and Lurda (2008) who indicated that NNETs' increased anxiety about their accent and pronunciation impacted upon their English teaching and interactions, which could lead to the failure of language teaching. Tang's (1997) study revealed similar results that NETs were superior in terms of speaking, accents and pronunciation, and according to Moussu (2006) NNETs' shortcomings included the foreign accent, insufficient knowledge of culture, and the lack of self-confidence. These shortcomings could result in the over reliance on teaching grammar rules rather than focussing on pragmatic language development and use.

Smith et al. (2007) highlight that teachers taught as they were taught, and the strongest predictor of language teaching success was the teacher having successful foreign or second language classroom learning experiences themselves. This is particularly relevant to Thailand as the historical English educational difficulties are self-perpetuating.

Lasagabaster and Sierra's (2004) studied 76 EFL undergraduate students who completed a Likert scale questionnaire about their preferences toward NETs' and NNETs' English teaching. Their results showed that students generally preferred to learn with NETs, but the differences in preferences for NETs and NNETs were based on specific language skill areas. The respondents preferred NETs for skills of speaking, pronunciation, and writing and listening, however preferred NNETs when learning grammar.

Liu and Zhang (2007) reviewed 65 third year EFL students of how they perceived differences between NETs and NNETs and focussed on attitude, teaching methodology and educational results. They found no statistically significant difference between the two teacher groups. The students perceived both groups as competent and hardworking.

There is a clear difference of how native and non-native teachers are perceived. Madrid and Canado (2004) identify these differences and highlight that the level of preference is related to the educational proficiency of the student, suggesting that as the competency rises, the preference shifts from non-native to native teachers of English. They go on to say that there is no statistical difference between how native and non-native English teachers are viewed.

When reviewing relevant research data related to Thailand, the diversity of perception was related to cultural differences. Phothongsunan S and Suwanarak K (2008) focused on non-native English teacher perceptions of native English teachers and highlight the students preference of NETs (as seen by Thai English teachers) as they provide a better learning environment, where students feel more relaxed and are able to model their language skill acquisition.

Bray L (2009) in her reflective account of her experiences as a native English teacher in Thailand focuses on cultural aspects of the education environment and how it influences students' behaviours. She implies that Thai students feel more comfortable in the native English teacher classroom as it is more relaxed and focusses on the utility of English rather than the description of the English language. The students have a genuine opportunity to practice the use of English with a native English teacher, which she suggests is not the case with her Thai English teaching counterparts, who frequently use Thai only in the classroom.

2. METHODOLOGY

In order to gain a holistic understanding of the data, it should be reviewed in its entirety. A reductionist experimental design that attempts to reduce the data to numbers to be compared using inferential statistics, would not provide an in-depth understanding of emerging themes. The preconception of expectation that leads to quantitative research is juxtaposed to the phenomenological paradigm. Dr Mayoux (1989) clearly sets out the advantages of qualitative research as being a more accurate reflection of a complex reality that leads to a better understanding. The recording of data as is, rather than prior selection of data criterion as in

experimentation or survey formulation, is seen as more reliable as the researcher is not influenced by expectations or the fear of consequences.

POPULATION AND PARTICIPANTS (SUBJECT OF THE STUDY)

The sample group of 158 undergraduate English major students, studying at UBRU, were from three intact cohorts and were a purposive convenience sample. All of the students were in their 3rd year and were engaged in a 16-week 'Writing English 3' (extended writing) module, taught by the researcher at the time of data collection. The sample had experienced both native and Thai English teachers although the majority of their educational experience was mainly with Thai English teachers. All of the students had studied English for a minimum of 10 years prior to commencement of their undergraduate studies. The full-time weekday students (two cohorts) were aged between 19 and 23 years old with approximately 90% being female. The part-time weekend students (one cohort) were older, approximately 70% female, with the majority being employed in a diverse array of jobs including, but not exclusive to, secretarial work, teaching, police, army, and self-employed business owners.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The most common sources of data collection in qualitative research are interviews, observations, and review of documents (Patton 2003). This research is an in-depth Inductive Thematic Document Analysis, which emphasises pinpointing, examining, and recording patterns (or "themes") within written data (Guest et al 2012), with an ethnographic component, as it is rooted in the culture of Thai and Native English teachers in Thailand as perceived by Thai students, and is based on qualitative document analysis (Maxwell 2013, Patton 2002, Thomas et al 2004).

RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

Two instruments are used.

- 1) The data instrument was in the form of a written essay with the title 'Write a 300-350 word, compare and contrast essay reviewing native and Thai English Teachers'. 158 5-paragraph essays were collected. Creswell (1998) introduces four types of qualitative data collection: interviews, observations, audio-visual methods, and documentation. He further indicated that documents should include an official record of written open-ended questions. Creswell (1998) stated that there were four advantages of written data: (1) the actual words for participants would remain, (2) the data can be accessed at any time, (3) it was an unobtrusive source of collecting information, and (4) the data could be utilized as written evidence.
- 2) Given (2008) clearly states that in qualitative research, the researcher is 'the primary research instrument' as their cognitive role in the research process is implicit in the phenomenological research paradigm. Within the context of this research, that means, critical, analytical, and creative thinking were used during coding, cyclic inductive reasoning and axial coding, coding group generation, using coding maps, and the identification of themes. There was also extensive memoing of researcher thoughts, ideas, and experiences that occurred during the research process.

CONSTRUCTION AND EFFICIENCY OF THE INSTRUMENTS

The construction of the students essay title was made as part of the students' practice of extended writing skills and formed part of their formal written assessment. The parameters of the essays should aid the identification of coded information as the students had previously reviewed compare and contrast essay structure and had practiced writing about the three most important comparisons and the three most important contrasts when writing a 350 word five paragraph essay of this type. The efficiency of this instrument is high as it stratifies the data, prior to review and analysis, into distinct code categories.

The construction of the instrument follows the typical process of qualitative research as described by Mackey and Gass (2005). That is, transcription, reading, coding, code grouping, repetitive axial coding, the generation of coding maps and the identification and generation of themes leading to greater understanding. The primary instrument is the logical, critical, analytical, and creative inductive thinking of the researcher.

The efficiency of this instrument is slow as it relies heavily on the cognitive ability of the researcher/analyser. The transcribing of all the data into a digital format was very time consuming, as was the identification of codes and code groups, axial coding, code-map generation and review, and theme identification and generation. The entire process was conducted manually and no qualitative/analytical technology or software was used.

DATA COLLECTION

The data collection took place during the middle of the 2nd semester 2557 (November). The essays were graded. The essays were returned to the students and they were then asked if the information that they had provided could be used in research. They were all given free choice and they expressed full agreement. They returned the graded essays to the researcher, which were then duplicated. The originals were given back to the students. All respondent identification, including names and university I.D. numbers were removed from the duplicate essays. The essays were then randomly mixed and were randomly allocated a number (1-158). This was done so that reference to the source data could be made during the analytical process. The original grammar used by the participants remains unchanged, therefore all illustrative examples of data responses are provided 'as written' by the participants.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis was conducted in a formal process as described by Westbrook (1994), Zhang and Wildemuth (2009), and Taylor-Powell (2003). This structure is outlined below.

- 1) First reading to generate a general overview of the data.

This was followed by recording general overview perceptions in the form of memoing. Data transcription of included material followed highlighting accepted data.

At the time of data transcription, large amounts of the text were omitted for the following reasons.

- **Repetition:** Where a student repeated an idea, concept or perception within an essay.
- **Introduction:** Where the introductory paragraph indicated perceptions that were discussed in greater detail in the body of the text.
- **Conclusion:** Where the conclusion was a summary of previously discussed material.
- **Ambiguity:** Where the student offers a perception but it was not clear whether it referred to NETs or TETs.
- **Clarity:** Where it was unclear what the student was trying to describe.
- **Grammar:** Where the wrongful use of grammar prevented meaning from being conveyed.
- **Personalisation:** Where the perceptions were overtly directed toward the researcher as opposed to NETs in general.
- **Content:** Where the students had wrongly followed the directions of the essay and had offered no relevant information or did not write about NETs and TETs.
- **Platitudes:** Comments such as “*all teachers are wonderful*”, “*all teachers love their students*”, “*all teachers love teaching*”, or “*teachers teach so students can learn*”, etc.
- **Contradictory data where the student writes a statement that they then refute:** Example “*Thai teachers can teach English pronunciation good but they pronunciation poor so they cannot teach pronunciation good*” [An actual quote].
- **Physical attributes:** Where the student comments on skin colour, eye colour, nose shape, average size, etc.
- **Copied/plagiarised data.**
- **Banal Statements:** Example “*Thai teachers teach Thai good*”, which was frequently stated when the student highlighted the benefit/preferences for native English teachers.

Following the omission of data the total volume remaining was 12823, words compiled of 741 separate data segments, made up of phrases and sentences. The longest single data item was 77 words in length and the shortest was 5 words in length. Each data entry related to a specific perception and could thus be coded.

2) Second reading of transcribed data to code the data and to formulate a code list.

The transcribed data was divided into 24 initial codes. Many of the data entries fell into two or more initial code groups. The data entries were further divided by the following criterion.

- The data item was written in a positive/neutral way.
- The data was written in a negative way in that it identified a perceived teacher/teaching deficit.
- The data was directly related to NETs.
- The data was directly related to TETs.

3) Generation of code groups and axial coding.

This was done following the generation of cognitive code maps that identified code links, see appendix A, B, C, and D. Cognitive links between codes and the frequency of shared data between the links were the criterion used to generate code groups.

- 4) Re-review of data in light of axial coding.

The data, codes, and code links were repeatedly re-reviewed to a point where the researcher was unable to identify any other code groups that could adequately define the data. Five code groups were identified and the initial codes were ascribed to one of these code groups. One initial code was rejected from the code groups as only 1 data item referred to the code and was related to physical attributes.

- 5) Generation of thematic code map. (Appendix E)
- 6) Identification of themes. (Appendix E)

3. FINDINGS

Initial codes: The initial codes were identified during the 2nd reading and subsequent re-reading of the original data. Some alterations were made in light of axial coding and some of the original definitions and code label wording was expanded.

The frequency of a data item being identified is not taken as being more real or true over a data item that was infrequently written. All perception data has to be acknowledged as true as it is what the students independently identified. Frequently cited perceptual items indicate common perceptions held by many participants, but does not denote its level of importance.

A total of 24 initial codes were elicited to categorise the transcribed data. At this stage the 741 data items reviewed were allocated to one or more codes leading to a total of 1388 allocated data items being spread between the initial codes, due to data items being in more than one code. The presentation of this numerical information is to aid understanding of the process and is not for statistical purposes. Each of the following codes is followed by the code definition and two illustrative data examples (*italics*). The initial codes were:

- 1) **Teacher Personality** - This code relates to aspects of personality, such as, kind, ‘caring’ etc. and includes comments that use the word personality. - *“Personality Thai English teacher are kinds, take care students, smile sweetly”, “Native teachers have such a personality they are quite natural”*.
- 2) **Teacher Confidence** - This code relates to all comments, both positive and negative, that relate to the confidence level of the teachers. - *“Foreign Teacher [native] confidences makes students pay attention in class”, “sometimes thai teacher don’t know that sometimes the errors they make them unconfident when started teaching. That problem make the student confuse “What’s true – What’s wrong?”*
- 3) **Student/Teacher Attentiveness, Enjoyment, Interest** - This code relates to all statements that relate to student/teacher attentiveness, enjoyment, and/or interest. - *“Thai English teachers always sit on chair it make student lack of interest and make very bored atmosphere in class”, “They [native] only explain at the first time then give activity to students, that meant students no time to look outside from their class, or they can not bored and sleep during class. Moreover, the students can get knowledge by fun and easy way.”*

- 4) **Over Acting** - This code describes a behavioural trait of exaggerated mannerisms. - *“Native teachers doesn’t have a style over acting” - “Thai teachers is like over acting to make student have trust them”*.
- 5) **Student/Teacher Confidence** - This code relates to any comment that relate to increasing or reducing student confidence. - *“When learn with a native English teacher do not understand we are afraid to communicate with confidents”, “Thai English teachers they always focus a grammar first so it make the student have no confidence when they speak English”*
- 6) **Trust** - All comments related to trust - *“The style of Thai teachers is make student have trust them”, “english teacher more trust student then thai teacher”*.
- 7) **Attractiveness (removed during the development of code groups)** - Any Comments that relate to perceived attractiveness.
- 8) **Stress** - All comments related to student/teacher stress. - *“Native speakers will have modern teaching methods, diverse, strategies in speech easy to understand, enjoy, not boring, and don’t stress too”, “Most of the Thai English teachers classes are quite stressfully”*.
- 9) **Speaking/Using English/Thai in the Classroom/Homework** - All data that relates to Speaking English in the classroom by students and/or teachers. – *“Native teachers teach only in English and it is good result for the students and the students can practice to listen a native English accent which the students will speedily learn English”, “Thai english do not speak english but can make students easy to understand in Thai but can not to practice english, and lack of knowledge”*
- 10) **Student Preference** – This code refers to any expressed or implied preferences of teaching style, teacher status, whether native or Thai, or any other statement identifying which teacher group is perceived as better. - *“native teacher can practice students about skill of reading, writing, and speaking good more than Thai English Teacher”, “The Thai English Teachers can easy explain more than The Native English Teachers and can good explain about Writing subjects and Reading subjects more than The Native English Teachers”*.
- 11) **Teacher Knowledge, Lesson Content and/or Teacher Limitations** - This code refers to any comments regarding perceived limitations of teachers - *“Native English teachers make their knowledge and substance in the lesson so interesting”, “The usual thing that Thai English teacher do in class are only read from text book because not knowlege then the students only repeat and memorize to get score. The students have only to listen. This cause make students bored and asleep during class, so make students loss to get knowledge, and some groups of students think ‘they can read by themself at their home’”*.
- 12) **Teacher Motives** - What the students express as teacher motives - *“Native English teacher quiet serious in this topic [talking]. They want to teach their students can talk and write in English.”, “Thai teacher want student to good exam more than can speak English”*.
- 13) **Expressed as Important** - Information that the students identify as important to themselves - *“The conversation, English use rate more and English proficiency has more important than use the grammar tense with the native English teachers”, “Thai English teachers think that the times are not important and they musn’t be on times”*
- 14) **Teacher Ability** - What the students express as teacher abilities - *“Native English teachers able to pronouncing accent, phonics and stress for correct speaking skills”, “The Thai teacher able can teach students in Thai and English, but the native English teacher can teach only English”*.
- 15) **English Grammar** - All references to the use of/teaching English grammar - *“using writing and using grammar correctly the native English teacher is better than the Thai English*

teacher”, *“Thai teacher when they teach they will worry about grammar more than how the student can get Or can understanding someone in English”*.

- 16) **Student Practice, Understanding, Learning, and Ability** - Students expressed ability to understand, learn, and/or practice in class - *“They [native teachers] can practice students about skill of reading, writing, and speaking good more than Thai English Teacher”, “Thai English teachers are understood need to detail on exercise or homework in Thai for easy understanding of Thai students. But it make Thai student didn’t practice English skill”*.
- 17) **Teacher Duties, Punctuality** - All expressions of teacher duties - *“Native English Teachers aren’t come to class late and have many trick and good game for increase efficiency or funny teach students”, “Thai English often don’t manage their teaching before class, they just come to class late and open the book and teach, read what is there on the lines”*.
- 18) **Teacher Attitudes** - Students’ perceptions/expressions of teacher attitudes - *“Native English teacher have characteristic are kind, teach funny, take care students, teach student are have punctual”, “Thai English teachers interested only the students who are talented students”*.
- 19) **Student/Teacher Expectations** - Students’ perceptions of teachers’ behavioural expectations of students and visa versa. - *“A Native English teacher expect the students to raise their hands, ask questions”, “They [Thai teachers] do not expect the students much to rise their hands and ask questions. It is considered to Thai English teachers a sort of rude, if a students raised their hands and says his or her opinion”*
- 20) **Student/Teacher Connectivity** - Student references to the connectivity between students and teachers - *“The native English teacher . . . is good because they interest and pay attention to every student in the class”, “Thai teach only good student an not interest in low student”, “Students are more connected to Thai teacher because they are more likely to have same attitude, belief and value”*.
- 21) **Teaching Methodology/Classroom Activity** - Students direct reference to teaching methods - *“Native teacher will always have students analyse and research [which] allows students can discover things by themselves”, “The Thai teachers always teach in books. This makes students only remember things in the books”*.
- 22) **Responsibility for Learning** - Where a student refers to whom is responsible for learning - *“The native teachers do not give the students lecture of write it down, but they emphasise the students responsible to practice themselves, seeking, learning on self, and they include to give an entertain when teaching, that make the students happy in class”, “Thai teach to pass exam get good score only”*.
- 23) **Culture / Corruption** - Where a statement refers to Thai/Native English culture or is culture dependent - *“they [native English teachers] have a strategy in the modern learning process that different from thailand”, “[when] a Thai [teacher] enters the classroom the students will be quiet until they are allowed to talk. They are regarded as good behaviour of Asian cultures”, “Sometime Thai English teachers choose to pay some money to can be a teacher by without examination”*
- 24) **Plagiarism** - Where a student refers to copying and or sharing exam answers or homework. - *“Native English teacher will not receive copy homework and will not give score to students who copy or do not make ideas into homework by themself”, “Thai teacher makes students copy homework or spend money to someone do homework to them. A Thai English teacher still receives students' homework and give score so look like Thai English teacher is very nice”*

Code Groups: The code groups were identified and labelled following exhaustive cyclic axial coding and re-reviewing of perception data items and initial coding. This inductive, deductive process enabled the twenty-four initial codes to be collapsed into five code groups. The five code groups are:

- 1) Use of L1 (Thai) in the EFL classroom
- 2) Culture
- 3) Teaching Methodology and Instruction
- 4) Teacher Attributes and Effectiveness
- 5) Student Preferences.

4. DISCUSSION

Code Groups: Each of the five code groups is discussed in turn giving the students perceptions of Thai English teachers and Native English teachers, with illustrative raw data examples. A brief discussion is then provided with some reference to literature. All illustrative student perceptual data quotes are written as originally written by the participants, including grammar and spelling errors. They also contribute to illustrating the discussion in the participating students' own words.

Code Group 1 - The use of L1 (Thai) in the EFL Classroom: The use of L1 in the EFL classroom is often debated. This research clearly identified a large number of students' perceptions that raise this issue. Three initial codes contribute to this code group and include 'Student Confidence' (code 5), 'Trust' (code 6), and 'Speaking/Using English/Thai in the Classroom/Homework' (code 9).

Sharma (2006) indicated that the use of L1 in a language classroom is at the centre of the debate. In the data, there was a clear indication that the students were also divided on this issue. The issue of L1 use appears to be directly related to the students' confidence, understanding, and proficiency using the target language (English). Illustrative comments include "*Sometime student be no confidence or shy to speak, and don't understand*" [with native teachers], or "*When learn with a native English teacher do not understand we are afraid to communicate with confidants*". An alternative perspective that focusses on the Thai English teacher is "*Some students may be more confident to try to speak English which the teacher is Thai*", or, "*Thai English teachers they always focus a grammar first so it make the student have no confidence when they speak English*". Whilst the second of these two TET directed comments uses grammar as a basis for low confidence using English, it is clear that student confidence will influence their use of English. It is interesting to note that there is also an indication that the student feels more relaxed using English with a Thai English teacher. Although this can be countered with the following perception, "*Thai English teacher almost speak in Thai always and do not speak English*", thus indicating the lack of English use in the EFL classroom where the English teacher is Thai.

Many of the comments related to the benefits of using L1 (Thai) in the classroom are primarily related to understanding complicated information or new concepts. The following data example highlight this. "*When I'm not understand something I can ask my teacher and I can speak thai*". Whilst the use of Thai (L1) is seen as useful to aid understanding and improve information sharing, alternative perceptual views were offered. Here the students attempt to provide reasons

for Thai language use in the EFL classroom. *“Thai English do not speak English but can make students easy to understand [in Thai] but can not to practice [English], and lack of knowledge.”* Here the student is identifying the lack of English skills development when Thai is used in the EFL classroom. An alternative perception to this is offered by another student who wrote *“Thai English teacher could be shy to speak in English because it is not their own language, They probably scare or uncomfortable to say or speak english out.”* Here the student suggests that Thai is used by TETs because of shyness. An important perspective is *“It might be some words that they [Thai teachers] do not know how to pronounce them so they just don’t say it. This is the easy way for Thai teacher to forget what they have learn”*, and clearly indicates that the students believe that not using English is a path to forgetting English and is indicating the perception of reduced teacher knowledge. This is an interesting perspective and could explain a recent open letter in the Bangkok post that highlights the Thai Ministry of Education’s research that found only 6 out of 43,000 Thai English teachers were fluent in English (Kantabutra 2015).

When reviewing the data about the use or non-use of L1 with NETs, a very different perspective is offered. There is a clear recognition that using English with native English teachers is considered an advantage. *“Native teachers teach only in English and it is good result for the students and the students can practice to listen a native English accent which the students will speedily learn English”*, and *“When the students study with the native English teachers, the students communicate in English so they practice to speak.”* These data items clearly indicate that the students perceive that they practice speaking English more with NETs and that it is beneficial. They also connect this increased practice with pronunciation and advanced learning, as in *“Native teachers communicate and teach in English, it makes the students to practice their listening skill, and they also practice a correct pronunciation. A student can pronunciation a word better than before”*, or *“Native English teachers can teach how to pronounce and stress words correctly”*.

One student went on to suggest a need for native English teachers, saying *“I think we should have native teachers to teach English for the Thai students. If we want to use efficiency English because Native English teachers they use English all of the time in their class, it is cause of Thai students are familiar with that until they can understand English and they can increasing English skills”*. Here the student identifies a perceived preferential benefit of studying with native English teachers in relation to the use of spoken English in the EFL classroom.

Those who support the maximum use of English in the EFL classroom suggest that the more a student is exposed to the target language, the more quickly they would learn. Environmental emersion forces the student to use the target language and was the only way to succeed (Curtin, 2005; Turnbull & Arnett, 2002). Whilst this view is evident in the data, an alternative perception of beneficial L1 use is also evident. Student perceptions clearly indicate that they can understand grammatical and linguistic concepts more easily when an explanation is given using their first language. He (2012) indicates that it could be an advantage for English teachers to use the students’ L1 in EFL education setting when appropriate. This was highlighted by Rose (1999) who suggested that both the mother tongue (L1) and the target languages should be used together as this would be helpful when clarifying grammar, vocabulary, pragmatics and cultural difficulties. However, Sharma (2006) stated that excessive and frequent use of L1 can only enable students to communicate in their first language.

Code Group 2 – Culture: Where native teachers teach English as EFL teachers, there is, inevitable a mixing of cultural identities. This research clearly identified a large number of students’ perceptions that raise this issue. Four initial codes contribute to this code group and include ‘Teacher duties / Punctuality’ (code 17), ‘Student/Teacher Connectivity’ (code 20), ‘Culture/Corruption’ (code 23), and ‘Plagiarism’ (code 24).

“Language is a part of a culture, and culture is part of a language” (Jaing, 2001). Culture has raised a debate in most EFL contexts since language should not be taught without culture (Tseng, 2004). The focus of this section is the cultural influence on EFL education in Thailand. Culture has been discussed in chapter two and will now be re-reviewed in light of the data. It has been clearly established that EFL education in Thailand utilises traditional education models of grammar/translation and rote learning with an aim of passing multiple-choice exams as a way of establishing student EFL development. It has also been established that teachers tend to use methodologies that they experienced during their own education. Researcher experience has also identified a strong Thai cultural patriotic stance that rejects any direct critique and/or suggestion for educational methodological acceptance of change, or indeed, a need for change. This stance is also related to Thais not losing face. The open acknowledgment that foreigners can contribute to policy and practice development within Thai EFL education is difficult for Thais to accept. This creates a repetitive cycle of stasis. Couple this with Thais perception of time management and accepted plagiarism, which is endemic in Thailand (Songsriwittaya et al, 2009), it is unsurprising that EFL education is progressing more slowly in Thailand than most other countries where English is acknowledged as the formal 2nd language. “If we are finally getting serious about improving the English competency of our [Thai] students, I suggest that we make remedial classes available for teachers nationwide” (Kantabutra, 2015). The above cultural perceptions were evident in the data and will now be explored, firstly looking at the students’ perceptions of native English teachers and then followed by a review of Thai English teachers as each cultural area is explored.

Native English teachers are seen as punctual by the Thai students which is in keeping with western cultural norms. “*The Native English teachers always serious about time more than the Thai teachers and have enthusiastic more than them*”, “*Native English teachers that they are strict about the time*”, “*Native English teacher are strict and come to the class on time*”, “*Native English teacher are punctual people*”, and “*Native teachers is very on time more than Thai English teachers*” are a brief selection of student perceptions related to western culture and timekeeping. The students also perceived native English teachers as using differing methodologies and is illustrated in the following student data examples. “*Native English Teachers aren’t come to class late and have many trick and good game for increase efficiency or funny teach students*”, “*native teachers are very serious about teaching responsibility, be methodological, always comes on time and polite, different from thai teachers*”. “*They [native English teachers] have a strategy in the modern learning process that different from Thailand*”. So there is a clear differentiation of perception of native English teaching using culturally different teaching methods. When reviewing plagiarism, the students clearly identify perceptual differences between Native and Thai English teachers. “*Native English teacher will not receive copy homework and will not give score to students who copy or do not make ideas into homework by themself*”, whereas, “*Thai teacher makes students copy homework or spend money to someone do homework to them,*” and “*Thai English teacher will check how the students can*

pass the test". A Thai English teacher still receives students' homework and give score so look like Thai English teacher is very nice", are all clear student perceptual illustrations of plagiarism being culturally accepted.

Thai English teachers timekeeping was also frequently perceived by the students and is clearly identified in the data, as follows: "*Thai English Teachers always late to class more than Native English Teachers*", "*Thai English teachers always come to the class rather late*", and "*Thai English teacher comes to class quite late, also the time when teaching they always stopped before time*".

Additional perceptual cultural comments mentioned or indicated teaching methodology "*Thai English Teachers are not active, teach easy and come to class very late*", "*Thai English often don't manage their teaching before class, they just come to class late and open the book and teach, read what is there on the lines*", with one student specifying what needs to be changed; "*Thai English teachers should come to teach on time. They should care more about teaching, that would make a Thai English teacher much more quality than it is, they should speak more English to the students so they [the students] can have a better experience*". Some students also perceived their Thai English teachers as; "*Thai English teachers expect the students to behave humble and very polite quiet and neat*", and "*do not expect the students much to rise their hands and ask questions*". In fact "*It is considered to Thai English teachers a sort of rude, if a students raised their hands and says his or her opinion*". In addition to the perceived behavioural norms of Thai students in the presence of their Thai English teachers, some students also made direct reference to their perceptions of corruption. They stated; "*Sometime . . . Thai English teachers choose to pay some money to can be a teacher by without examination*", and "*Sometimes Thai English teachers strict about 'Thai Teaching System' it's meant to pay some money or corruption to can be teacher*". Alternatively, the students identified that "*Students are more connected to Thai teacher because they are more likely to have same attitude, belief and value*" and that "*A Thai English teacher will understand the Thai culture and the difficulties faced by Thai students learning English*". These are important perceived cultural differences that the students have regarding native and Thai English teachers.

Culture and understanding cultural difference is vital in the EFL classroom. The cultural difference between native and non-native (Thai) English teachers provide a much greater educational experience for the students. It also provides real sharing and learning opportunities to adapt educational practice. Educational EFL programmes that include information about L1 and L2 cultures are more successful (Neito and Booth, 2009) and are also beneficial for both Native and Thai English teachers.

First language culture should be incorporated into the target language curriculum as students can then reflect on their own culture and be better able to understand target language features (Krieger 2005). Both native and Thai English teachers need to have a basic understanding of both Thai and native English cultures so that they can effectively facilitate EFL education.

Code Group 3 – Teaching Methodology and Instruction: How English teachers prepare and deliver EFL education is important. This research clearly identified a large number of students' perceptions that raise this issue. Five initial codes contribute to this code group and include

‘Stress’ (code 8), ‘English Grammar’ (code 15), ‘Student Practice/Understanding/Learning/Ability’ (code 16), ‘Teaching Methods/Activity’ (code 21), and ‘Responsibility for Learning’ (code 22).

It is clear that successful EFL learning is highly dependent upon effective teaching (Dixon et al 2012), irrespective of whether the EFL teacher is a native English speaker or a non-native English speaker, and includes the attributes of the teacher and the instruction methodologies used in the EFL classroom. Utilising an appropriate teaching methodology is therefore very important. There are many methodological theories that are used to justify instruction methods and all have their advocates and have varying levels of efficacy. However, regarding the Grammar-Translation Approach, which dominated European and foreign language teaching from the 1840s to the 1940s, in a modified form continues to be widely used in a few parts of the world today including Thailand. The results of using this method creates frustration for students and makes few demands on teachers. It is still used where understanding text is the primary focus of foreign language study and there is little need for a speaking knowledge of the language and it is taught using L1. Consequently, though it may be true to say that the Grammar-Translation Method is still practiced, it has no academic champions. It is a method for which there is no theory. There is no literature that offers a rationale or justification for using the grammar-translation method, nor that attempts to relate it to issues in linguistics, psychology, or educational theory (Fitriyanti and Soraya, 2011). Many of the dissatisfactions of experiencing the grammar translation method are identified in the student perception data and will now be explored, firstly focussing on native English EFL teachers and subsequently on Thai English teachers.

The following student perception data entry is succinct and clearly indicates methodological diversity. *“Native speakers will have modern teaching methods, diverse, strategies in speech easy to understand, enjoy, not boring, and don’t stress too”*. As opposed to *“thai teacher teach from book and not move in class makes us boring”*. These are interesting examples as they clearly identify the differences of teaching methodologies used by native English teachers when compared with Thai English teachers. Further exploration of the data confirms this in more detail. *“Using writing and using grammar correctly, the native English teacher is better than the Thai English teacher”*, was a common perception among the students, as was *“I think foreign teacher have good pronunciation and grammar.”* This implies that the students perceive the ease with which native English speakers use grammar correctly. However, a number of students indicated that they think *“thai teachers teach the grammar better the native English teachers”*, and that, *“Thai teachers teach the grammar easy for understand but native teachers are not.”* Some students went on to indicate that *“The Thai English would mostly focus on grammar and correct English structure”*, and that, *“Thai English teachers very serious about grammar and writing but they don’t talk.”* It is clear that the Thai English teachers are perceived to focus very much on grammar and translation rather than understanding. Some students were more explicit with their perceptions and directly identified the utility of the grammar-translation model. *“Commonly Thai teachers pay more attention to traditional grammar-translation method”* and *“Thai English Teachers seem to favour the traditional methods like grammar, translation and audiolingualism and mainly focus on grammar rules and language accuracy”* These perceptions indicate that students are aware of the teaching methods employed by Thai English teachers and can differentiate between NETs and TETs. The students go on to comment that *“Thai English teachers can explain difficult grammar points in student native tongue”*, and that the respondent

students perceived their *“Thai English teachers to teach grammar more understand than native English teacher because Thai English teacher have easy and describe to grammar”*. The students went on to say that *“Thai English teachers are able to teach English grammar better than the Native English teachers”*, although the students also recognised and perceived that *“Thai teacher when they teach they will worry about grammar more than how the student can get Or can understanding somemore in English”*. Despite this students’ preference for TETs to teach grammar, others also recognised that *“The Thai English teacher often uses the wrong grammar in teaching. It makes the students using grammar wrong as well”*.

The students’ perceptions of NETs also included practicing English and they stated that *“We practice listening and speaking with native English teacher,”* and that *“Students can understand clear pronunciation of native English teachers”*. The students perceived that *“Native English teachers always serious about listening and speaking and they teach the students can talk and connect with foreigners in the complete conversation”*. *“Native English teachers do not sit on the chair. They usually stand and walk to talk many things about material and give activities. The students get more and more ideas . . . that meant the students are also get knowledge easily from fun”*. *“Native teacher they will have more style or more activities to make the student understand English, think in English and speaking English”*. Some of the students expressed their difficulty with NETs stating that *“When we learn with a native English teacher do not understand we are afraid to communicate”* and one student stated that she *“didn’t understand in studing when native English teacher teaching in class”*.

It was frequently perceived and stated that when the students did not understand something, they were able to communicate in their mother tongue with TETs. A typical comment was *“When I’m not understand something I can ask my teacher and I can speak thai”*. Additionally it was stated that it was easier with TETs as *“The students easy to learn because they teach by thai language”*. However it was also perceived that *“With a thai Teacher the student wasn’t learn pononciation, how to speak the different word”*. Further, a student stated that *“Sometime they [TETs] forget something, some students cannot understand about material that they teach. This caused make students cannot do exercise or homework, finally students cannot get score the result is bad graded, but no student like to get low grade”*. The students also indicated the results focussed methods rather than focussing on understanding and stated that *“Thai English teaches speaking repetitiously, difficult to listen and understand”*, and that *“Thai English teachers are understood need to detail on exercise or homework in Thai for easy understanding of Thai students. But it make Thai student didn’t practice English skill”*. So, many of the students stated that whilst the methodologies employed by TETs are easier, they also recognised that they were less effective and at many times boring.

Conversely, the students perceived and identified that *“Native teacher will always have students analyse and research [which] allows students can discover things by themselves”*. Students perceived that *“Native English teachers always to do activities in the class”* and that *“It is fine for the students to speak up [and] the native English teacher would like those kinds of things”*. *“They [NETs] always want many questions from students”*. In fact, one student stated that *“A Native English teacher expect the students to raise their hands, ask questions”*. The students also frequently noted that *“Native English teachers will explain and give some example to the students”* and went on to perceive that *“Native teacher technique is very important and*

interesting to attraction the students make attendance to the class". The students went on to explain this by identifying that *"Native English teachers usually use many medias or materials for example, the doll, the pictures, music, map. And video, etc. It can make the students interested, active and have fun in the class"*, and that *"The native teacher have a lot of activities to make their students excited and have fun"*. Not only did the students express feelings of excitement and fun when learning with NETs, they also noted that NETs used a variety of methods and that *"the students are also get knowledge easily from fun"*.

The use of classroom environment was also noted. The students perceived that *"Native English teachers do not sit on the chair they usually stand and walk to talk many things about material and give activities. The students get more and more ideas"*. Whereas Thai English teachers were perceived as *"always sit on their chair and talk about only their informations that they want to give their students"*, and that *"The Thai teachers always teach in books"* or *"is teaching directly from books"*. *"They Thai English teachers have less action and activities therefore make their teaching unexcited and noninterest"*. However some students noted that Thai English teachers do move and that they *"would write grammar and vocabularies on the board then students learn by rote"*. This was perceived by some to be so that *"students studying with a Thai English teacher can memorise so they can use their knowledge for test"* as *"Thai English teacher focus on remembering and not understand"*. One student encapsulated the above sentiments with the following data item. *"The usual thing that Thai English teacher do in class are only read from text book then the students only repeat and memorize to get score. The students have only to listen. This cause make students bored and asleep during class, so make students loss to get knowledge"*.

A general sentiment from the students was *"Native teacher they will have more style or more activities to make the student understand English, think in English and speaking English"*.

However, it may be difficult for the EFL teacher to identify and use one method that applies to all classroom settings and student requirements. Samaranayake (2015) encourages English teachers to review the advantages and weaknesses of a variety of methods and then to blend various methods in order to meet the specific linguistic needs of the students.

Code Group 4 – Teacher Attributes and Effectiveness: The effectiveness of English teachers is important and is closely related to teacher attributes. This research clearly identified a large number of students' perceptions that raise this issue. Seven initial codes contribute to this code group and include 'Teacher personality' (code 1), 'Teacher Confidence' (code 2), 'Over Acting' (code 4), 'Teacher Knowledge, Content &/or Limitations' (code 11), 'Teacher Motives' (code 12), Teacher Attitudes (code 18), and 'Teacher Expectations (code 19).

It has previously been highlighted that it is not ethnicity alone nor that simply being a native or non-native speaker of the target language is able to be used to identify and determine how effective an EFL teacher is. The effectiveness of the EFL teacher is, however, related to a number of criteria. Astor (2000) suggests that a qualified teacher of English should be well versed and competent in pedagogy, methodology, and psycho and applied linguistics. What makes a good teacher is very important as it affects the quality of the EFL teaching and learning process. In addition to the above criteria, Borg (2006) adds personal qualities and attitudes as also being important. All of these criteria above must be learned and practiced by language

teachers. Arikan et al (2008) further added the following qualities: having individual teaching strategies, maintaining positive student teacher interactions, creating a positive classroom atmosphere, being a role model, being friendly to students, teaching with effective classroom materials and by using technology, and giving positive reinforcement.

The following student perception data entries clearly indicate that they are aware of teacher attributes and indicate the effectiveness of teachers. *“Native teachers have such a personality they are quite natural”* and their *“confidences makes students pay attention in class”*. Alternatively, some students noted that, *“The style of Thai teachers is like over acting to make student have confidence and make students trust them”*, whereas, *“Native teachers doesn’t have a style over acting.”* The students further noted that *“Thai English teacher could be not confidence shy to speak in English because it is not their own language,”* and *“They probably scare or uncomfortable to say or speak it out.”* *“Sometimes thai teacher don’t know that sometimes the errors they make them unconfident when started teaching. That problem make the student confuse ‘What’s true – What’s wrong?’”* The students perceived the TETs as *“Most of Thai English teachers able speak English but not fluence”*. These data items indicate the perceived lack of knowledge or English skill used by TETs, which leads to a reduction of confidence. In some cases, it could lead to faulty English skill development. There was also an implied implicit knowledge of English by virtue of just being a native English speaker and this can be seen in the following data item. *“The English native will also have a native speaker’s knowledge of the English language, of course.”* There was also a clear differentiation between the perception of the level of advancement or difficulty between NETs and TETs. *“The content of the English courses directed by native English teacher are more advanced than those directed by Thai English teacher. Native English teachers teaches difficult but students are and enjoyable and happy so much. And the content are so good and easy understand.”* Despite this perceived higher level, *“Native English teachers make their knowledge and substance in the lesson so interesting.”* Whereas, *“Thai English teachers make students bore because their substance in the lesson.”* It is clearly indicated in the data that the students perceived the TETs as lacking in knowledge and that this impacted upon them. One of the data items clearly and succinctly indicate this perception. *“The usual thing that Thai English teacher do in class . . . are only read from text book because not knowlege then the students only repeat and memorize to get score. The students have only to listen. This cause make students bored and asleep during class.”*

The students perceived both NETs and TETs as being kind and this is indicated in the following two data items – *“Thai English teachers are kinds, take care students, smile sweetly”* and *“Native English teacher have characteristic are kind, teach funny, take care students, teach student are have punctual.”* However it was also noted that *“The native English teacher is good because they interest and pay attention to every student in the class.”* Whereas *“Thai English teachers interested only the students who are talented students”*.

What is important to note is that whilst the students perceived NETs and TETs differently in terms of attributes, the focus was on equity, knowledge, skill and methodological choice. These attributes, which improve effectiveness, are learned and therefore can be learned equally by TETs and NETs.

Code Group 5 – Student Preference: Student preference is an integral part of EFL education as it provides needed educational practice-delivery feedback. This research clearly identified a large number of students’ perceptions that raise this issue. Four initial codes contribute to this code group and include ‘Student/Teacher Attentiveness/Enjoyment/ Interest’ (code 3), ‘Student Preference’ (code 10), ‘Expressed as Important’ (code 13), and ‘Teacher Ability’ (code 14).

Students are by definition the recipients of EFL education. Their preferences must therefore be explored, acknowledged, understood and accommodated. It is clear that there is a growing recognition of students’ views and perceptions by researchers, which is important as this provides important feedback that can inform practice development.

Lasagabaster and Sierra (2004) showed that students preferred to learn with NETs in general. There were however differences when reviewed by skill, such as a preference for NETs when learning production skills including speaking and writing. However they also showed that there was a preference towards NNETs when learning grammar. Mahboob (2004) also indicated that NETs are perceived as better teachers of vocabulary and native culture, although also indicated that there was little difference between the perceptions of NETs and NNETs. However, Park (2009) found no overall preferences for NETs over NNETs at all.

These studies show there is little consensus with regard to preference or the ideal EFL teacher. NETs and NNETs both have advantages and disadvantages. Alseweed (2012) goes on to state that it is unfair to judge one group based on their disadvantages. What is important are the English skills of the EFL teacher and the Teaching skills of the teacher, and not whether an EFL teacher is native or non-native.

These mixed results are validated and reflected in the mixed student perceptual data in this research. The students’ perceptions of preference were mixed and they frequently expressed a strong preference for NETs over TETs, whereas other students expressed preferences for TETs over NETs, although this was less frequent, and was more often related to grammar education specifically. Although the student data did not always use the word preference, preference was indicated where the data clearly indicated that one teacher group or teaching method was considered more enjoyable or better. The following data items illustrate this. *“The native teacher have a lot of activities to make their students excited and have fun,”* and they *“make students awake all of the time”*. One student identified this perception in a more complete way with the following data item. *“They [native] only explain at the first time then give activity to students, that meant students no time to look outside from their class, or they can not bored and sleep during class. Moreover, the students can get knowledge by fun and easy way.”* Thai teachers were also seen by some students as *“teachers teaches students very easy and funny and enjoyable but not serious.”*

It was also perceived and noted that *“Thai English teachers always sit on chair it make student lack of interest and make very bored atmosphere in class.”*

Some students were much more explicit and directly stated, *“I prefer studying with native English teachers”*, or *“I prefer Native English Teachers to Thai English teachers”*. Some reasons were also noted for this were the students perceived native English teachers as *“for speak most*

people think the native English teachers teach better the thai teachers”, and “the native English is better than the Thai English teacher.” “A native English teacher is able to teach English better than a Thai English teacher because all skills are taught properly by a native teacher such as listening, speaking, reading and writing.” Some students also considered “native teachers are better in terms of teaching grammar” as they “using writing and using grammar correctly the native English teacher is better than the Thai English teacher,” although this was not a common perception. Many of the students did, however, indicate that “Native English Teachers are linguistically superior”, and that they “can teach about Speaking Subject good more than the Thai English Teachers” and “can practice students about skill of reading, writing, and speaking good more than Thai English Teacher”. The students also indicated that “native English teachers provide more accurate pronunciation and better expressions to students.” These preferences for NETs were not universal, as perceived and indicated in the following data items. “Most people think the native teachers are better the thai teachers but I don’t think that” and “I like Thai English teacher give a good mark more than a native English teacher” and “I think thai teacher teach me understand more better than native English teacher.”

There was a clear and frequent preference for TETs with regards to grammar. *“I think thai teachers teach the grammar better the native English teachers”, and “I think Thai English teacher can teach grammar better than native English teacher”. Some students went further and indicated that “The Thai English Teachers can easy explain more than The Native English Teachers and can good explain about Writing subjects and Reading subjects more than The Native English Teachers”. An additional perception was “I think that Thai English teacher are better for beginners”. This perception was coupled with “the Thai teacher able can teach students in Thai and English, but the native English teacher can teach only English” and that “Thai students able can understand the Thai English teacher more than the native English teacher.” It was the ability to use L1 in the EFL classroom that was given as the reason for preferring TETs when learning grammar. “Thai English teachers can able to explain difficult grammar points in student native tongue” and that “Thai English teachers good at in grammar and they able to explain the lesson with bilingual.”*

The students indicated a mixture of preferences. What appears important is that both TETs and NETs are perceived by the students as having advantages and disadvantages. The data reflects other studies that have looked at student perceptions and is a good indication of the need for TETs and NETs to work more closely together to meet the individual and collective needs of the EFL students.

Themes: The themes have been determined following a thorough review of the data, coding, and the development of the code groups as the product of inductive and deductive reasoning. The code groups reflect how the respondent students see both native and non-native (Thai) English teachers that they have experienced. These code groups were used to develop the finalised themes, which are (1) Pedagogy – the art and science of teaching and education, and (2) Impact and Affect. The word ‘affect’ in this theme title refers to the noun meaning of feelings or emotions. That is, theme (1) is what EFL teachers do and theme (2) is the impact of what EFL teachers do, as determined by the respondents’ data. Theme 1 draws from the first 4 code groups whereas theme 2 draws from all 5 code groups. This data is represented graphically in the Research Process Thematic Map (Appendix E).

Theme one: Pedagogy: The respondents considered both NETs and NNETs as having good English proficiency in teaching different English language skills, which included four main areas: (1) oral fluency, (2) writing and grammar, (3) vocabulary, and (4) culture.

Oral fluency: Regarding oral fluency, NETs were perceived as fluent speakers with an accurate English accent. The students stated that learning listening and speaking skills with native English teachers helped them practice their pronunciation and English speaking skills. Additionally, they can also experience the utility and demonstration of correct grammatical use by native English speakers when they communicated orally in class. The use of ‘standard’ English by NETs was perceived as most likely to aid Thai English learners to experience fluent, accurate pronunciation of English. The students could also benefit by recognising their own pronunciation errors and thus avoiding the errors that can create the misunderstanding of native English speakers when communicating orally.

The students perceived more opportunities to practice speaking and listening skills when their teacher was a native English teacher. This finding is supported by Benke and Medgyes’ (2005) who found that most NETs encouraged learners to speak English and hence, learners were forced to stay in a micro emersion environment. Some students did however perceive and indicate that they found it difficult at times to understand NETs due to the speed of their speaking. Furthermore, some students stated that they were shy to use English in front of a NET because of the fear of making a mistake and losing face. So, despite the students recognising the advantages of studying spoken English with NETs, some of them still preferred TETs as they were considered easier to understand, even though their pronunciation was considered inferior to NETs.

It was also noted that NETs were far more selective in the language used and the methods employed when teaching listening and speaking skills. The students stated that NETs used more appropriate methods with regard to the students’ different English proficiency levels. Negative commentary mainly focussed on the perceived inaccuracy of pronunciation of English by NNETs and concerns about learning mispronunciation. This concern is clearly identified in the literature by Lee (2010), Lasagabaster & Sierra (2004), and Mahboob (2004) among many others.

Writing and Grammar: The students were positive when identifying writing. There were two main areas. Firstly they highlighted the TETs’ focus on grammar and the rules which they stated was best taught by TETs. By doing so, the students could develop a clear image of the rules and realise how and when to use English grammatical forms precisely. However, Huang and Brown (2009) identified that most NNETs tended to apply a test-oriented educational system when teaching grammar, which is typical of the grammar translation method employed by TETs, and thus by doing so, teaching grammar was not done for its pragmatic use. Many of the students in this study identified that learning grammar that way was not meaningful for them and just led to confusion, boredom, and/or reduced motivation. They also stated that they found it difficult to remember this ‘descriptive’ information and relate it to writing ability. Thus, even after years of grammar lessons the students were often unable to write a simple sentence correctly. Students expressed confusion about different grammar rules such as tense, word variation, sentence structure and so on. Secondly, the students also expressed a preference for NETs as they

focussed on differing writing skills and encouraged free writing practice in relation to appropriate proficiency level reading. The students stated that it was more interesting and gave them a greater level of understanding when learning with NETs. No negative aspect of learning writing skills with NETs was shared by students.

Vocabulary: Some students' perceptions related to the extent of words known by NETs and how they were pronounced. The mispronunciation of words and the perceived correct pronunciation offered by NETs was highlighted as a reason for wanting to be taught by NETs. The extent of NETs vocabulary was also noted, but was expected, as it was also recognised that the English vocabulary was far larger than the Thai vocabulary. Some students also perceived TETs as having a lower English vocabulary than their NET counterparts. It was also noted that TETs were able to easily explain new vocabulary by using Thai, whereas NETs spent more time (taking longer) to aid student understanding by drawing, acting, and using simple English. Some students expressed a preference for being able to use Thai in the classroom to understand new vocabulary, whereas, some preferred the NETs methods of explanation, which the students perceived as more enjoyable and memorable.

Culture: Very few perceptions were related to NETs' culture. However many students indicated how culture effected their experiences in the classroom. These cultural effects were related to classroom activity, perceived classroom restrictions, and the assessment processes and perceived aims of education.

In relation to classroom activity, many students noted that the NETs were 'active' in class and rarely sat down. They were described as always being on time, selecting appropriate teaching materials to meet learners' needs and goals, using many or modern methodological approaches in the classroom and that their educational sessions were stimulating and interesting. Benke and Medgye's (2005) noted that the respondents complemented NETs on the selecting of teaching materials. The students also noted that they were able to practice real conversations in English. When perceiving and identifying Thai cultural influences in the classroom, the students noted that frequently TETs were late to class and spent their teaching time sat down reading or working from textbooks. The students noted that they were often bored and found the learning of grammar rules this way as confusing. The students also noted that they had little English interactive communication practice and spent their time practicing repeat or rote exercises, which they identified as not stimulating.

Moreover, the students perceived restrictions in the TETs classroom, which included the inability to ask the teacher questions, as it was not culturally accepted to question a teacher. TETs were however, perceived as allowing the students to chatter amongst themselves in Thai and not listen to any active speakers. The students were also expected to just read the books and regurgitate the content without any recognition for the need to show understanding. Alternatively, NETs were seen as being very open and encouraged their students to frequently ask questions, although Benke and Medgye's (2005) noted that NETs might not be able to answer students' questions due to the differences in cultural background, which created a communication gap between teachers and students. In addition, the students noted that NETs were strict about classroom chatter and that they expected the students to listen to their teacher as well as each other.

Education aims and assessments were also identified as being culturally different. The students perceived that TETs taught English with a focus on passing exams whereas NETs assessments were about what the students understood. The students perceived the TETs assessment as easier, especially given that the students were allowed to copy from the internet and share their answers to assessment questions with each other. The students noted that copying in any form was not acceptable to NETs. This appears to reflect the collective supportive aspects of Thai culture as opposed to the recognition of individual responsibility of western educational systems.

The students also identified their affinity with the TETs with whom they shared a cultural heritage.

Theme two: Impact and Affect: This theme specifically relates to the effects of pedagogy as perceived by the respondent students. The teaching styles used by NETs, which were frequently complimented by the students, were the use of various activity approaches in the EFL classroom. They were interested in learning and expressed excitement at impending classes which they enjoyed without boredom. This was somewhat different from the respondents' perceptions of TETs who frequently used a didactic textbook approach, which focused on test results and which the students perceived and expressed as boring and limited in effectiveness and understanding.

Whilst the NETs and TETs were both considered caring, it was the NETs who were singled out as caring for all students, irrespective of their proficiency level, whereas TETs were perceived as caring most for the higher proficiency students. Students remarked that they preferred the non-judgemental attitude of NETs. Students were also encouraged to ask questions by NETs whereas TETs were seen as reluctant to take questions. The reason for this was given as the cultural norm in Thailand of not questioning teachers.

The student perceived themselves as being much more involved in the NET EFL classroom rather than being passive recipients when learning with TETs. This was perceived to be a result of the utility of activity based methodologies being used by NETs, as opposed to the more traditional didactic, grammar translation methods used by TETs. The students clearly stated they preferred writing, and listening and speaking classes when taught by NETs, but preferred grammar lessons with TETs, as complicated explanations could be provided in Thai. One student specifically stated that TETs were better for EFL beginners and NETs were better for higher proficiency learners, particularly as they had more opportunities to practice English and were more able to understand as they progressed.

Many students did, however, find it more difficult to communicate with NETs and some of them expressed anxiety about making mistakes or not being understood. Other students, however, preferred the opportunities to interact in English and get feedback from NETs. They also stated they preferred NETs as they perceived them as providing 'correct' English pronunciation.

Many students expressed a preference for being able to use Thai in the EFL classroom as they found it difficult to understand what was sometimes said in English by NETs. However, some students preferred the English only classroom because of the diversity of ways the NETs use to provide understanding. This diversity was seen as interesting and fun, and kept the students

awake. Whilst some students liked the opportunity to use Thai in the EFL classroom to gain understanding, they also stated that sitting and just listening to the TETs using Thai was boring.

The students liked that the focus of EFL education with NETs was on English proficiency and understanding. However, they also liked the test-results focused methods used by TETs as they perceived that it was easier to get higher grades.

Some of the students perceived NETs as being more patient and encouraging than TETs, especially when trying to use grammar correctly, and particularly when working with lower proficiency students in the EFL classroom.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The primary reason for this research was to explore EFL student perceptions of native and non-native English teachers. Specifically, it sought to examine Thai university undergraduate EFL students' perceptions of their NETs and TETs. The transcript data was collected in November 2014 from 158 students undertaking a writing 3 module within the Thai Rajaphat University system.

The initial raw written data was qualitatively analysed using inductive and deductive reasoning as part of an in-depth Inductive Thematic Script Analysis. 24 codes were identified to categorise and organise the data following the transcription of accepted data. These data were then further reduced to five code groups. The five code groups then led to the formulation of two emergent themes.

In this study, the participants were able to express their perceptions of their NETs and TETs. The results revealed the students are aware of and acknowledge the advantages of both NETs and TETs in teaching specific language skill areas. They indicated the two teacher groups strengths and weaknesses complemented each other and were both necessary.

Having opportunities to learn English from both native and non-native English teachers seems to be of real value to the Thai EFL students. The students did not however, indicate that either teacher group was superior to the other. The results did indicate a difference in how each teacher group taught English and how their performance and competencies, as well as the impact of the teaching, were perceived by the students during English teaching sessions.

It is hoped that this study and the results will be useful and of benefit to all those involved in EFL education, particularly in Thailand. The initial research questions were answered and the recommendations based upon the application of this research are as follows.

IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) In this study, the students stated they liked the use of L1 (Thai) in the classroom as it reduced student anxiety and aided the understanding and clarification of complicated information. The use of L1 should therefore continue to be acceptable. However, it also needs to be the second option behind the use of English as ultimately it is not possible to learn English

pragmatically in a classroom where Thai is the language most often used. Simply put, Thai talking time reduced English exposure and practice time.

- 2) The students clearly indicated a dislike for the use of textbooks as the primary teaching method employed by TETs and a strong preference for interactive, varied, activity based methods employed by NETs. TETs should, therefore widen their educational repertoire and utilise a varied approach that meets the academic needs of the students.
- 3) According to the data, the students indicated the advantages and disadvantages related to NETs and TETs English teaching in different language skill areas. It is therefore suggested that EFL programme developers and educational leaders assign NETs and TETs to deliver specific language skills based on these results and that equal advancement opportunities be afforded to both NETs and TETs. For instance, NETs should be assigned to teach listening and speaking courses and writing courses, with TETs focussing on grammar, translation, and Thai cultural topics. NETs should be given the same support for continued education and career advancement opportunities.
- 4) The students in this study affirmed the essential features of teachers' knowledge and abilities, which should be given high priority in determining effective teachers. For this reason, educational institutions that offer EFL programmes must pay greater attention to the English skills and teaching abilities of their EFL teachers. This includes setting a minimal English standard and utilising an internationally recognised test (TOEFL) to monitor staff ability. This is particularly important in Thailand given their persistently very low English proficiency score (EF EPI English Proficiency Report, Fifth Edition, 2011-2015). Greater knowledge and utility of varied pragmatic researched based teaching methods that reflect the needs of the EFL students are also recommended for TETs and NETs. Being a native English speaker is not enough. A good EFL teacher, whether native or non-native must be able to demonstrate both proficient English language skills and knowledge of pragmatic language teaching methodologies in order to meet the educational and linguistic needs of the students.
- 5) In this study the students provided rich data about their preferences for teaching methodologies. All teaching staff should consider their own educational practice and incorporate where possible what the students say they prefer, except where it has been shown previously to be detrimental to EFL education, such as, TETs focussing on test scores and giving better grades rather than focussing on understanding and pragmatic context based practice, as is done by NETs, as perceived by the students studied.
- 6) In this study, the volume of data and the time constraints have meant that further analysis of the data is possible. The use of qualitative data analytical computer systems would aid this deeper analysis.
- 7) The qualitative data of this study were collected from 158 student essays where the students were able to freely provide their individual perceptions. It is suggested that future studies collect additional data from face to face interviews, learning journals, and classroom observations. The data could also be used to develop Likert type online questionnaires that could be used to validate these results and enable inter university and cross-cultural comparison. Using these various methods of data collection and the results would be more comprehensive, reliable, and valid.
- 8) There is little doubt that NETs and TETs are important in EFL teaching in Thailand. Therefore, future studies in Thailand should investigate NETs and TETs perceptions of themselves and each other, as well as the faculties' perceptions of TETs and NETs. This will provide valuable information about effective English language teaching.

- 9) This study focused on Thai EFL undergraduate students within one university. Future research should consider involving students and/or teachers from other cultural and language backgrounds, within the ASEAN community, within ASIA and throughout the world.
- 10) This current study revealed students' perceptions of preferred teaching methodologies and classroom activities. Future research should explore how the implementation of their views actually impacts the pragmatic delivery of EFL education and results of such changes. EFL students could benefit from such cooperation and a genuine recognition that their perceptions are considered important.

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7. REFERENCES

- [1] AL-OMRANI, A. *Perceptions and attitudes of Saudi ESL and EFL students towards native and non-native English-speaking teachers. PhD Thesis. ProQuest Dissertation database. 2008*
- [2] ALSEWEED, M. *University Students' Perceptions of the Influence of Native and Non-native Teachers. English Language Teaching; Vol. 5, No. 12, 2012*
- [3] ARIKAN, A. TASER, D. SARAC-SUZER. *The effective English language teacher from the perspectives of Turkish preparatory school students. Eğitim ve Bilim, 33(150), 42-51, 2008*
- [4] ARVA, V. MEDGYES, P. *Native and non-native teachers in the classroom. System, 28(3), 355-372, 2000*
- [5] ASTOR, A. *A qualified non-native English speaking teacher is second to none in the field. TESOL Matters, 10(2), 18-19. 2000*
- [6] BARRATT, L. KONTRA, E. *Native English-speaking teachers in cultures other than their own. TESOL Journal, 9(3), 19-23, 2000*
- [7] BENK, E. MEDGYES, P. *Differences in teaching behaviour between native and non-native speaker teachers: As seen by the learners. In E. Llurda (Ed.), Non-native language teachers: Perceptions, challenges and contributions to the profession p.p. 195-216. Springer, 2005*
- [8] BLOCK, D. *English and globalization. Routledge, 2002*

- [9] BORG, S. *The distinctive characteristics of foreign language teachers. Language Teaching Research*, 10(1), 3-31. 2006
- [10] BOYLE, J. *Native-speaker teachers of English in Hong Kong. Language and Education*, 11(3), 163–181, 1997
- [11] BRAINE, G. *Non-Native Educators in English Language Teaching. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Publishers. 1999*
- [12] BRAY, L. *Cultural dimensions for a foreigner teaching English in a Thai university. TOSL in Context – Pedagogies of Connection 209 Special Edition, Volume S2. 2009*
- [13] COOK, V. *Going beyond the native speaker in language teaching. TESOL Quarterly*, 33(2), p.p. 185-209. 1999
- [14] CRESWELL, J. PLANO-CLARK, V. *Principles of Qualitative Research: Designing a Qualitative Study. Office of Qualitative & Mixed Methods Research, PPP, University of Nebraska. 1998*
- [15] CRYSTAL, D. *English as a global language. Longman. 2003*
- [16] CUTIN, M. *Teaching practices for ESL students. Multicultural Education*, 12(3), 22-27. 2005
- [17] DAVIES, A. *The native speaker: Myth and reality. Multilingual Matters. 2003*
- [18] DIXON, L. ZHAO, J. WU, S. SU, J. BURGESS, R. GEZER, M. SNOW, C. *What we know about second language acquisition: a synthesis from four perspectives. Review of Educational Research*, 82(1), 5-60. 2012
- [19] EF EPI English Proficiency Report. Fifth Edition. www.ef.com/epi
<http://media2.ef.com/~/media/centralefcom/epi/downloads/full-reports/v5/ef-epi-2015-english.pdf> 2014
- [20] EF EPI English Proficiency Report. First Edition. www.ef.com/epi
<http://www.ef.co.th/~/media/efcom/epi/pdf/EF-EPI-2011.pdf> 2011
- [21] EF EPI English Proficiency Report. Fourth Edition. www.ef.com/epi
<http://media.ef.com/~/media/centralefcom/epi/v4/downloads/full-reports/ef-epi-2014-english.pdf> 2014
- [22] EF EPI English Proficiency Report. Second Edition. www.ef.com/epi
http://www.ef.co.th/~/media/efcom/epi/2012/full_reports/ef-epi-2012-report-master-lr-2.pdf 2012
- [23] EF EPI English Proficiency Report. Third Edition. www.ef.com/epi
<http://www.ef.co.th/~/media/efcom/epi/2014/full-reports/ef-epi-2013-report-master-new.pdf> 2013
- [24] FILHO, E. *Students' perceptions of nonnative ESL teachers (Masters thesis, West Virginia University, 2002*
- [25] FITRIYANTI. R. SORAYA, A. *Grammar Translation Method. https://novaekasari09.wordpress.com/2011/06/12/grammar-translation-method/. 2011*
- [26] FOLEY, J.A. *English as a lingua franca: Singapore. International Journal of the Sociology of Language*, 177, 51–65. 2006
- [27] GASS, S. SELINKER, L. *Second language acquisition: An introductory course. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Publishers. 2001*
- [28] GIVEN, L. *The SAGE Encyclopaedia of QUALITATIVE RESEARCH METHODS, Volumes 1&2. A SAGE Reference Publication. 2008*
- [29] GUEST, G. MACQUEEN, K. NAMEY, E. *Applied thematic analysis. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. 2012*

- [30] HE, A. *Systematic use of mother tongue as learning/teaching resources in target language instruction. Multilingual Education*, 2(1), 1-15. 2012
- [31] HOLLIDAY, A. *The struggle to teach English as an international language. Oxford, England: Oxford University Press. 2005*
- [32] HUANG, J. BROWN, K. *Cultural factors affecting Chinese ESL students' academic learning. Education*, 129(4), 643-653. 2009
- [33] JAING, W. *Handling "culture bump". ELT Journal*, 55(4), 382-390. 2001
- [34] KANTABUTRA, B. *Ministry aims to cut foreign English Tutors BP Nov 13*
<http://www.bangkokpost.com/opinion/opinion/766592/teachers-apply-here> 2015
- [35] KIRKPACTRIC, A. *Teaching English across cultures. What do English language teachers need to know to know how to teach English? Paper presented at the English Australian Conference. 2006*
- [36] KRIEGER, D. *Teaching ESL versus EFL: Principles and practices. English Teaching Forum*, 43(2). 2005
- [37] LASAGABASTER, D. SIERRA, J. *University Students' Perceptions of Native and Non-native Speaker Teachers of English. LANGUAGE AWARENESS, Vol.11, No. 2. 2002*
- [38] LASAGABASTER, D. SIERRA, J. *The Nativeness Factor: An Analysis of Students' Perceptions.*
http://www.laslab.org/upload/the_nativeness_factor:_an_analysis_of_student%C2%B4s_preferences.pdf. 2004
- [39] LEE, C. *Native versus Non-native: A Literacy Teacher Educator's Story.*
<https://ejournals.library.ualberta.ca/index.php/langandlit/article/viewFile/9434/7445>. 2010
- [40] LEE, J. *The Native Speaker: An achievable model? ASIAN EFL JOURNAL, Volume 7, Issue 2, Article 9, June. 2005*
- [41] LIGHTBOWN, P. SPADA, N. *How languages are learned. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 1999*
- [42] LIU, M. ZHANG, L. *Students' perceptions of native & non-native English teachers' attitudes, teaching skills assessment and performance. Asian EFL Journal*, 9(4), 157-166. 2007
- [43] LUI, J. *Non-native-English-speaking professionals in TESOL. TESOL Quarterly*, 33 (1), 85-102. 1999
- [44] MACKEY, A. GASS, S. *SECOND LANGUAGE RESEARCH Methodology and Design. LAWRENCE ERLBAUM ASSOCIALES, PUBLISHERS. 2005*
- [45] MAHBOOB, A. *Native or non-native: What do students enrolled in an intensive English program think? In L. Kammhi-Stein (Ed.), Learning and teaching from experience: Perspective on non-native English speaking professionals (pp. 121-147). Ann Arbor, MI: University of Michigan Press. 2004*
- [46] MAHBOOB, A. *The NNEST Lens: Non Native English Speakers in TESOL. Cambridge Scholars Publishing. 2010*
- [47] MAXWELL, J. *Qualitative Research Design – An Interactive Approach 3rd edition. SAGE Publication. 2013*
- [48] MAYOUX, Dr. L. *QUALITATIVE METHODS.*
<http://www.proveandimprove.org/documents/QualMethods.pdf>. 1989

- [49] MCNIELL, A. *Some characteristics of native and non-native speaker teachers of English. In N. Bird (eds.), Language and learning. Papers presented at the Annual International Language in Education Conference, Hong Kong, 1994*
- [50] MEDGYES, P. *Native or non-native: who's worth more? ETL Journal Volume 46/4 October 1992, Oxford University Press. 1992*
- [51] MEDGYES, P. *When the teacher is a Non-native Speaker. <http://teachesl.pbworks.com/f/When+the+teacher+is+a+non-native+speaker.PDF>. 1993*
- [52] MOUSSU, L. LLURDA, E. *Non-native English-speaking English language teachers: History and research. Lang. Teach. (2008), 41:3, pp.315-348. 2008*
- [53] MOUSSU, L. *Native and Non-native English-Speaking English as a Second Language Teachers: Student Attitudes, Teacher Self Perceptions, and Intensive English Administrator Beliefs and Practices. PhD Thesis, August 2006, Purdue University, Indiana. 2006*
- [54] NEITO, C. BOOTH, M. *Cultural competence: Its influence on the teaching and learning of international students. Journal of Studies in International Education, 14, 406-425. 2009*
- [55] NOON-URA, S. *English Teaching Problems in Thailand and Thai Teachers' Professional Development Needs. English Language Teaching: Vol. 6, No. 11. 2013*
- [56] NUNAN, D. *English as a global language. TESOL Quarterly, 39, p.p.235-261. 2001*
- [57] PARK, E. *The Korean university students' preferences toward native English teachers. Modern English Education, 10(3), 114-130. 2009*
- [58] PATTON, M. *Qualitative Research & Evaluation Methods - 3 Edition. Sage Publication. 2003*
- [59] PATTON, M. COCHRAN M. *A Guide to Using Qualitative Research Methodology Medecins Sans Frontieres. 2002*
- [60] PHOTHONGSUNAN, Dr. S. SUWANARAK, Dr. K. *Native and non-native dichotomy: Distinctive stances of Thai teachers of English. ABAC Journal VI 28, No 2 (May-August, pp.10-30). 2008*
- [61] REVES, T. MEDGYES, P. *The non-native English speaking EFL/ESL teacher's self-image: An international survey. System, 22 (3), 353-367. 1994*
- [62] ROSE, K. *Teachers and students learning about requests. Culture in second language teaching and learning. 1999*
- [63] RUBIN, D. *Effects of language and race on undergraduates' perceptions of international instructors: Further studies of language and attitude in higher education. Paper presented at the Annual Meeting of the International Communication Association, Albuquerque, NM. 1995*
- [64] SAMARANAYAKE, S. *The Best Method in EFL/ESL Teaching. International Journal of English and Literature IJEL, Vol 5, Issue 5, Oct 2015*
- [65] SHARMA, B. *Mother tongue use in English Classrooms Journal of NELTA, 11 1-2, p.p. 80-87. 2006*
- [66] SMITH, C. BUTLER, N, L. HUGHES, T, A. HERRINGTON, D. KRITSONIS, W, A. *Native vs. non-native teachers of English in Polish schools-personal reflections. The Lamar University Electronic Journal of Student Research, 4. 2007*
- [67] SONGSRIWITTAYAL, A. KONGSUWAN, S. JITGARUN, K. KAEWKUEKOOL, R. *Engerneering Students' Attitude towards Plagiarism: A Survey Study http://www.ineer.org/events/iceeiceer2009/full_papers/full_paper_212.pdf. 2009*

- [68] STERN, H. H. *Fundamental concepts of language teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 1983
- [69] TANG, C. *The identity of the nonnative ESL teacher: On the power and status of nonnative ESL teachers*. *TESOL Quarterly*, 31(3), 557-580. 1997
- [70] TAYLOR-POWELL, E. RENNER, M. *Analyzing Qualitative Data G3658-12 University of Wisconsin-Extension Cooperative Extension Madison*. 2003
- [71] THOMAS, J. HARDEN, A. OAKLEY, O. SUTCLIFFE, K. REES, R. BRUNTON, G. and KAVANAGH, J. *Integrating qualitative research with trials in systematic reviews*. *BMJ* 2004; 328: 1010-1012. 2004
- [72] TSENG, C. *The use of culture in teaching English as a foreign language*. Texas A&M University- Kingsville, Kingsville, Texas. 2004
- [73] TURNBULL, M. ARNETT, K. *Teachers' uses of the target and first languages in second and foreign language classrooms*. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 22, 204-218. 2002
- [74] ULATE, V. *Insights towards Native and Non-native ELT Educators*. *Bellaterra Journal of Teaching & Learning Languages & Literature*, Vol. 4(1), Jan-Feb 2011, pp. 56-79. 2011
- [75] WESTBROOK, L. *Qualitative Research Methods: A Review of Major Stages, Data Analysis Techniques, and Quality Control LISR 16*, 241-254. 1994
- [76] WIDDOWSON, H. G. *ELT AND EL TEACHERS: MATTERS ARISING*. *ELT JOURNAL*, 46(4), 333-339. 1992
- [77] WIRIYACHITRA, A. *English Language Teaching and Learning in Thailand in this Decade*.
https://www.academia.edu/11373994/English_Language_Teaching_and_Learning_in_Thailand_in_this_Decade. 2013
- [78] WORLD LANGUAGES and CULTURES. *Why learn languages? 10 good reasons why you should be learning a foreign language*.
http://www.vistawide.com/languages/why_languages.htm. 2010
- [79] ZHANG, Y. WILDEEMUTH, B. *Qualitative Analysis of Content*. 2009.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

CONCEPTUAL CODE MAP OF NUMBER OF POSITIVE/NEUTRAL CODED 'NET' DATA ITEMS WITH LINKS

N° Data Items (key)	
1-10	Data Items
11-20	Data Items
21-30	Data Items
31-40	Data Items
41-50	Data Items
51-60	Data Items
61-70	Data Items
71-80	Data Items
81-90	Data Items
91-100	Data Items
101+	Data Items

N° Code Links (key)	
1-5 links	
6-10 links	
11-15 links	
16-20 links	
21-25 links	
26-30 links	
31-35 links	
36-40 links	
41-50 Code Links	
Positive/Neutral perception	
Negative Perception	

APPENDIX B

CONCEPTUAL CODE MAP OF NUMBER OF NEGATIVE CODED ‘NET’ DATA ITEMS WITH LINKS

N° Data Items (key)	
1-10	Data Items
11-20	Data Items
21-30	Data Items
31-40	Data Items
41-50	Data Items
51-60	Data Items
61-70	Data Items
71-80	Data Items
81-90	Data Items
91-100	Data Items
101+	Data Items

N° Code Links (key)	
1-5 links	
6-10 links	
11-15 links	
16-20 links	
21-25 links	
26-30 links	
31-35 links	
36-40 links	
41-50 Code Links	
Positive/Neutral perception	
Negative Perception	

APPENDIX C

CONCEPTUAL CODE MAP OF NUMBER OF POSITIVE/NEUTRAL CODED ‘TET’ DATA ITEMS WITH LINKS

N° Data Items (key)	
1-10	Data Items
11-20	Data Items
21-30	Data Items
31-40	Data Items
41-50	Data Items
51-60	Data Items
61-70	Data Items
71-80	Data Items
81-90	Data Items
91-100	Data Items
101+	Data Items

N° Code Links (key)	
1-5 links	
6-10 links	
11-15 links	
16-20 links	
21-25 links	
26-30 links	
31-35 links	
36-40 links	
41-50 Code Links	
Positive/Neutral perception	
Negative Perception	

APPENDIX D

CONCEPTUAL CODE MAP OF NUMBER OF NEGATIVE CODED 'TET' DATA ITEMS WITH LINKS

N° Data Items (key)	
1-10	Data Items
11-20	Data Items
21-30	Data Items
31-40	Data Items
41-50	Data Items
51-60	Data Items
61-70	Data Items
71-80	Data Items
81-90	Data Items
91-100	Data Items
101+	Data Items

N° Code Links (key)	
1-5 links	
6-10 links	
11-15 links	
16-20 links	
21-25 links	
26-30 links	
31-35 links	
36-40 links	
41-50 Code Links	
Positive/Neutral perception	
Negative Perception	

APPENDIX E

THEMATIC MAP RESEARCH PROCESS

